

Computational Analysis of Nanoparticle Flow Dynamics in the 18th Generation of the Human Lung

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ABSTRACT

Nanoparticles, which are too small to be seen but can enter our bodies through breathing, cause damage to our lungs and air passageways, are degrading the quality of the air. They may ultimately result in serious health problems like asthma, COPD, and emphysema. The filtration system of the lung is investigated by modeling airflow and the movement of nanoparticles through it using fluid dynamics equations and Newton's second law for particle motion. An explicit finite difference scheme and specialized MATLAB code are used to solve nonlinear equations and establish the effect of oscillation frequency, mean permeability, and Reynolds number on air and dust particle behavior. The results demonstrate that the air and particle flow rate increased continuously as the breathing rate, Reynolds number, and average permeability of the porous medium increased.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nanoparticles, due to their extremely small size and unique physical and chemical properties, pose significant health risks when inhaled, as they can penetrate deep into the lung airways and alveolar regions, leading to respiratory and systemic diseases. The complex structure of the human lung, which is frequently represented as a porous medium, undergoes periodic variations in permeability as a result of breathing; yet, the majority of current research assumes constant permeability. Addressing this limitation, this research focuses on analyzing the effects of periodic permeability on two-dimensional viscous flow and nanoparticle transport in the 18th generation lung's airways. By

formulating the governing nonlinear equations and solving them using finite difference methods within a MATLAB code, this research provides a computational analysis of airflow dynamics and particle deposition. The findings are expected to inform the design of better inhalation treatments and health risk assessments by enhancing knowledge of how nanoparticles behave in actual lung circumstances.

Nanoparticles are minute substances with distinct physical and chemical properties, and they can be harmful to human health as they may settle in the lung airways when inhaled (Poland et al., 2008; R. Sturm et al., 2002). Extremely small nanoparticles—between 5.52 and 98.2 nm—are known to be

extremely dangerous to anyone who is exposed to them at work. They have been connected to a number of illnesses that impact the heart, lungs, and brain. According to the study of Tian et al. (2017) and Sturm (2013), particles with a diameter of around 100 nanometers can enter the lungs deeply and finally gather in the alveolar ducts, which are tiny air sacs that are in charge of gas exchange (Anju, Katiyar & Pratibha, 2017). It is more challenging to determine where irregularly shaped nanoparticles deposit within the lungs than spherical ones. These particles' uneven travel routes, their different aspect ratios, variations in inhalation flow rates, and the complex arrangement of the branching airways in the human lungs are some of the causes of this intricacy (Haber et al., 2003; Zhang & Finlay, 2005; Hinds, 1982).

Numerous branching structures and microscopic chambers make up the human lungs. Due to this intricate network, the lungs have been considered to be a porous medium or sponge in certain studies (DeGroot & Straatman, 2018a; Kuwahara et al., 2009). Others, however, view it as a permeable tube that permits substances to pass through (A. M. Siddiqui et al., 2017; A. Siddiqui et al., 2018). The anatomy of the lung and its narrow borders make it crucial to comprehend how particles behave in the airways (Anju; Katiyar & Pratibha, 2017). Kumari & Goyal (2017) examined the effects of oscillating constraints regarding the flow of a viscous liquid contained between two parallel plates arranged vertically, Kumari and Goyal conducted investigations.

Blood flow in a stenotic (narrowing) inclined artery with porous walls was examined by Chitra & Karthikeyan, (2018). Kori & Pratibha (2019a) investigated how a thick, incompressible fluid behaved when passing through a highly permeable material. According to another study, when inhaling, children and teenagers are more prone than adults to have bioaerosol particles lodge deeply in their lungs' alveoli (Sturm, 2016). The accumulation of nanoparticles causes the alveoli and air passages to relax or rupture, which results in a variety of respiratory diseases. Using the alveolar region as an internal biological filter, Saini & Katiyar (2015) assessed the lungs capacity to remove nanoparticles using generalized Navier-Stokes equations. DeGroot and Stratman employed volume averaging theory to predict human lung permeability in a recent study on the heterogeneity of alveolar duct

elasticity. Their method is based on the idea that the lung parenchyma is a porous material with mechanical properties that vary in space (DeGroot & Straatman, 2018b).

However, a thorough analysis of these studies shows that the majority of porous-medium and nanoparticle flow models either limit their research to the proximal generations of the lung (usually up to the 16th generation) or assume constant permeability. The investigation of how space-varying permeability and periodic breathing affect the flow and particle deposition in the extremely distal region of the lung, particularly in the 18th generation, where alveolar ducts predominate, has not received much attention in research.

The current study establishes a two-dimensional flow model with explicit periodic permeability variations in the 18th generation airways in order to address this problem. The model is improved over previous porous-medium and nanoparticle flow models because it anticipates nanoparticle transport and deposition in a more physiologically realistic manner by combining a generation-dependent distal lung geometry representation with a periodic breathing impact. We aim is to investigate the effects of the natural breathing cycle-induced periodic changes in permeability on two-dimensional viscous flow through the 18th generation of airways. The nonlinear governing equations are fully formulated and quantitatively solved using finite difference techniques. For the simulations and computational analysis, user-developed code based on MATLAB 2016 was utilized.

Anatomy of Lungs

The lungs are vital components of the respiratory system, which is responsible for gas exchange. Through the mouth or nose, air enters the body and swiftly passes into the pharynx. The lungs' large interior surface area aids in directing airflow to the right areas for effective gas exchange. The blood absorbs oxygen from the lungs. The human lung is made up of the trachea, bronchi, and bronchioles and has a branching tree-like structure (Figure 1).

Figure 01: Airway Branching of Human Lung (Price et al., 2019)

The airway tree consists of roughly 23 generations, starting at the trachea (generation 0) and ending at the terminal bronchioles (generation 23). The adult trachea measures roughly 1.8 cm in diameter and 23 cm in length. Asymmetric branching results from the right bronchus's greater width and narrower angle with the trachea. Small bronchi (generations 5–11) gradually decrease in diameter, shrinking from 3.5 mm to 1 mm. Approximately 3.9 mm in length and 1.09 mm in diameter, the conducting zone at the 11th generation has 2048 branches and a Reynolds number between 10 and 12 (Table 01). The diameter of alveoli ranges from 0.2 to 0.3 mm, and the tracheobronchial tree's diameter decreases with each generation. The respiratory zone, comprising bronchioles, alveolar ducts, and sacs (generations 17 to 23), is where gas diffusion and conduction occur. The respiratory system is separated into the lower tracheobronchial tree, which supplies air to the lungs, and the upper airways, which include the throat, nasal passages, and sinuses. With an adult lung capacity of roughly 5 liters, respiratory bronchioles can hold 2.5 to 3 liters of air.

Table 1: Lungs Airway Across Generation (Price et al., 2019)

Item	Generation (G)	Number (n)	Length (mm)	Mean Diameter (mm)	Re
Trachea	0	1	120	18.00	1480
Main Bronchus	1	2	67.60	12.20	1092
	2	4	19.00	8.30	803
Lobar Bronchus	3	8	7.60	5.60	595
Segmental Bronchus	4	16	12.70	4.50	370
	5	32	10.70	3.50	238
	6	64	9.00	2.80	149
Bronchi Wall	7	128	7.60	2.30	91
	8	256	6.40	1.96	53
	9	512	5.40	1.54	34
	10	1024	4.60	1.30	20
Terminal Bronchus	11	2048	3.90	1.09	12
	12	4096	3.30	0.96	6.78
Bronchiole Wall	13	8192	2.70	0.82	3.97
	14	16,384	2.30	0.74	2.20
	15	32,764	2.00	0.66	1.23
Terminal Bronchiole	16	65,536	1.65	0.60	0.68
	17	131,072	1.41	0.54	0.38
Respiratory Bronchiole	18	262,144	1.17	0.50	0.20
	19	524,288	0.99	0.47	0.11
	20	1,048,576	0.83	0.45	0.056
Alveolar Duct	21	2,097,152	0.7	0.43	0.030
	22	4,194,304	0.59	0.41	0.015
Alveolar Sac	23	8,388,608	0.50	0.41	0.008

Mathematical Model

Structural Arrangement

The alveolar duct is depicted as a circular tube with radius r in Figure 2. Instead of moving in a radial direction, the dusty air travels down the axis of the tube. A Newtonian, viscous, and incompressible fluid is involved in the laminar flow, which is fueled by a pressure gradient that varies with time.

Figure 02: The alveolar region is a circular tube with radial movement along the radius r and viscous airflow in the axial (z) direction (Kori et al., 2020)

Governing Equations

The continuity and momentum equations are used to study the dynamics of airflow in the lungs, particularly inside an oscillating porous structure (Kori & Pratibha, 2018).

The continuity equation, expressed in a cylindrical coordinate system, controls air flow,

$$\frac{\partial \rho_a}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r \rho_a u_r)}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial(\rho_a u_z)}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (1)$$

The continuity equation, expressed in a cylindrical coordinate system, controls dust flow,

$$\frac{\partial \rho_p}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r \rho_p v_r)}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial(\rho_p v_z)}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (2)$$

The governing equation of momentum in radial direction,

$$\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial t} + \frac{u_r}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{u_z}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} = -\frac{\epsilon}{\rho_a} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial z^2} \right) + \left(-\frac{\epsilon \nu}{k} u_r + k_f \frac{\rho_p}{\rho_a} (v_r - u_r) \right) \quad (3)$$

The governing equation of momentum in axial direction,

$$\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial t} + \frac{u_r}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} + \frac{u_z}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = -\frac{\epsilon}{\rho_a} \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z^2} \right) + \left(-\frac{\epsilon \nu}{k} u_z + k_f \frac{\rho_p}{\rho_a} (v_z - u_z) \right) \quad (4)$$

K, or permeability, is influenced by the porosity ϵ (Kleinstreuer & Feng, 2013) expressed as,

$$k(r) = \frac{K_0}{1 - a_0 \cos\left(\frac{\pi r}{a}\right)} \quad (5)$$

K_0 is a measure of mean permeability, and a_0 is the oscillation amplitude.

The governing equation for particle movement along the radial direction.

$$\frac{\partial v_r}{\partial t} + v_z \frac{\partial v_r}{\partial z} + v_r \frac{\partial v_r}{\partial r} = \frac{F_{d1}}{m} \quad (6)$$

The variable m stands for mass, while is the drag F_{d1} experienced by a sphere-shaped substance. The governing equation for particle movement along the axial direction.

$$\frac{\partial v_z}{\partial t} + v_z \frac{\partial v_z}{\partial z} + v_r \frac{\partial v_z}{\partial r} = \frac{F_{d2}}{m} \quad (7)$$

The way non-spherical particles are carried and deposited during fluid flow is described by a metric termed the particle shape factor (Kori & Pratibha, 2019b; Jones et al., 1995). This element is crucial for maintaining the geometrical structure of non-spherical particles and demonstrates the way the drag force differs between nanoparticles. Ratio of drag forces acting on various non-spherical nanoparticles and for the respective spherical counterparts with an equivalent volume is simply described by this factor (Kori & Pratibha, 2018).

In order to effectively simulate the effects of rhythmic breathing, heart-induced pressure fluctuations, and the respiratory system's periodic expansion and contraction, we included a time-dependent, non-dimensionalized oscillatory pressure gradient in the respiratory tract, as suggested in (Kori & Pratibha, 2019a).

$$-\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} = A_0 \sin 2\pi f t \quad (8)$$

Initial and Boundary Conditions

1. There is no airflow moving inward or outward along the airway duct's radius, and it is presumed that there is no change in the airflow's velocity along its axis.

$$u_r = 0, v_r = 0, \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} = 0, \frac{\partial v_z}{\partial r} = 0$$

2. When the system is at rest ($t \leq 0$), the system is inactive, so there is no fluid flow.

$$u_r = v_r = 0 \text{ and } u_z = v_z = 0$$

3. Because of the periciliary liquid layer's effect, the inner wall exhibits a no-slip condition.

$$u_r = 0, u_z = 0 \text{ and } v_r = 0, v_z = 0$$

Methodology

The nonlinear structure of the current equations makes it challenging to apply the same procedures under the necessary initial and boundary conditions, even though linear problems may frequently be solved exactly using analytical methods. To address this issue, we employed a numerical approach. For solving similar nonlinear equations, the finite difference method (FDM) (Kori et al, 2018), finite element method (Sera et al.,

2015), and finite volume approach(Koullapis et al., 2016) are commonly employed among the available techniques. Particularly for issues involving regular forms, the finite difference method (FDM) is the simplest and straightforward of these approaches. FDM is an appropriate choice for our problem since it deals with flow in a circular cylinder, which is a regular form. Thus, to solve the present problem, we also applied a finite difference numerical scheme. To discretize the axial velocity $U(R, Z, \tau)$, we denote it as $U_z(R_i, Z_j, \tau)$, or simply $((U_z)_{i,j})^k$. The structure of the computational mesh used in the analysis is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} R_i &= i. \Delta R \text{ and } i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M \\ Z_j &= j. \Delta Z ; \text{ and } j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N \\ \tau_k &= k. \Delta \tau ; \text{ and } k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, O \end{aligned}$$

Here, i, j, and k represent the indices for space and time. The step sizes are $\Delta R = 0.01, \Delta Z = 0.01, \Delta \tau = 0.001$ corresponding to the radial, axial, and time duration, respectively. To approximate all spatial derivatives, we employed central difference formulas, as described below:

$$\frac{\partial U_z}{\partial Z} = \frac{(U_z)_{i,j+1}^n - (U_z)_{i,j-1}^n}{2\Delta Z}$$

To approximate the first-order time derivative at the position (R_i, Z_j, τ_k) , we used the forward difference approach as follows:

$$\frac{\partial U_z}{\partial \tau} = \frac{(U_z)_{i,j}^{n+1} - (U_z)_{i,j}^n}{2\Delta \tau}$$

We obtained the velocity profiles at the $(j + 1)^{th}$ time level by using the discretization techniques previously mentioned, based on the velocity values for the corresponding equations at the $(j)^{th}$ time level.

Results and Discussion

We examined a cylindrical fluid channel at a distance of $2r$ that permitted a constant, laminar, and incompressible flow. In order to confirm the precision and stability of the numerical model, we evaluated different grid sizes 31×31 , and 51×51 along the axial direction before starting the major simulations. The most dependable results were obtained with a grid size of 31×31 , which was the recommended option.

Figure 03 : Validation of Computational Grid Convergence.

We use $\Delta R = 0.01, \Delta Z = 0.01, \Delta \tau = 0.001$ for numerical discretization. Both the air velocity and the particle velocity fields were obtained by directly solving the governing equations using this configuration.

$$\max \left\{ \frac{\Delta \tau}{\Delta Z^2} \right\} \leq 0.5$$

The results seem to have converged with an accuracy on the order of 10^{-3}

Table 02: The specified values

No.	Parameter	Amount
01	The density of Particle(ρ_p)	$2.5045 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$
02	The density of air (ρ_a)	1.2039 kg/m^3
03	Density based on the sphere's diameter (d)	$1 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}$
05	Velocity (U)	0.3 m/s
06	The particle mass (m)	$1.1514 \times 10^{-24} \text{ kg}$
07	Frequency (f)	1.2 Hz
08	Fluid viscosity parameter (ν)	$1.50293 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$

The values considered in this case fall within these intervals: $0.2 \leq Re \leq 1, 0.001 \leq Da \leq 0.1, 10 \leq \beta \leq 1000$, and $0.84 \leq \epsilon \leq 2$ (Anju; Katiyar & Pratibha, 2017).

Influence of Reynolds Number on the Internal Filtration System within Lung Airway

Impact of Breathing Frequency on the Performance of the Lung's Internal Filtration Mechanism

An important element in establishing the flow characteristics inside the respiratory pathways is the dimensionless Reynolds number. Between 4000 and 0.001, the number dramatically drops from the trachea to the alveolar sacs.

Assuming $\epsilon = 0.6$, $\beta = 10$, $K_0 = 0.1$, and $f = 0.2$, this work illustrates the variance in axial velocities of both fluid and particulate matter for Reynolds numbers ranging from 0.2 to 1.

Under the fixed parameters $\beta = 10$, $Re = 0.1$, and $K_0 = 0.1$, we investigate the response of air and dust particles over time to frequency fluctuations in the range $0.025 \leq f \leq 0.1$ in Figure 4. Because of the sinusoidal oscillation of the airway walls, air velocity first increases and peaks at $t = 0.2$. After this, the velocity just slightly decreases and stays comparatively constant. Nonetheless, a significant increase in air velocity is noted when the frequency rises from 0.2 to 0.6, highlighting the dynamic impact of breathing frequency on flow behavior.

(a)

(b)

(a)

Figure 04: Influence of Reynolds number on the dynamic flow patterns of (a) air and (b) dust particles.

During mid-airway generations (10–15), air velocity peaks at a Reynolds number of about 1, but as the flow reaches generation 18, where Re drops to 0.2, it noticeably decreases. Dust particle motion exhibits a similar pattern, with velocities gradually decreasing from generation 10 to 18. The main cause of this steady decrease in air and particle motion is increased viscous effects, demonstrating a gradual reduction of flow momentum as air moves over time toward the outer edges of the airways.

(b)

(a)

Figure 05: Influence of Frequency on the dynamic flow patterns of (a) air and (b) dust particles

In contrast, the velocity of the particles rises proportionally with an increase in breathing frequency. Because the increased particle speed encourages deeper penetration and deposition, this behavior increases the risk of particle retention in diseased lungs compared to healthy respiratory systems that are better able to control airflow and filtration.

Periodic Permeability in Airway Filtration

We examine the effect of periodic wall permeability in Figure 5 by varying the mean permeability K_0 between 0.1 and 3, assuming $\epsilon = 0.6$, $\beta = 10$, and $Re = 0.1$. It was determined that the axial velocities were substantially lower at $K_0 = 0.1$ than they were at $K_0 = 3$. By increasing K_0 the airway walls' permeability, reducing internal pressure, and fostering a more robust axial flow. As a result, air and particle velocities along the airway periodically increase.

(b)

Figure 06: Dynamics Effect of Periodic Permeability on the Flow Dynamics of (a) Air and (b) Dust Particles periodically increase.

The phenomenon previously shown with air is mirrored for dust particles, where an increase in mean permeability K_0 from 0.1 to 3 leads to higher periodic permeability of the airway walls.

5. CONCLUSION

Our findings reveal that Reynolds number, breathing frequency, and lung permeability collectively affect airflow and nanoparticle transport in the lung's porous media. At low Reynolds numbers (e.g., $Re = 0.1$), elevated viscosity significantly decreases particle velocity, promoting deposition along the airway surfaces. Conversely, higher breathing frequencies and increased permeability enhance airflow and particle movement, improving overall transport efficiency. These results offer valuable implications for aerosol therapy optimization and pollutant exposure assessment, particularly in conditions like asthma, COPD, and bronchitis. Future research should focus on integrating patient-specific airway models, capturing complex breathing patterns, and examining thermal, humid, and morphological influences on particle behavior. Integrating these enhancements with clinical validation will pave the way for precision-targeted respiratory treatments.

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